

Analysis of

The Impact of Virtual Reality on Chronic Pain by Ted Jones, Todd Moore, James Choo

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Abstract

The treatment of chronic pain could benefit from additional non-opioid interventions. Virtual reality (VR) has been shown to be effective in decreasing pain for procedural or acute pain but to date there have been few studies on its use in chronic pain. The present study was an investigation of the impact of a virtual reality application for chronic pain. Thirty (30) participants with various chronic pain conditions were offered a five-minute session using a virtual reality application called Cool! Participants were asked about their pain using a 0–10 visual analog scale rating before the VR session, during the session and immediately after the session. They were also asked about immersion into the VR world and about possible side effects. Pain was reduced from pre-session to post-session by 33%. Pain was reduced from pre-session during the VR session by 60%. These changes were both statistically significant at the $p < .001$ level. Three participants (10%) reported no change between pre and post pain ratings. Ten participants (33%) reported complete pain relief while doing the virtual reality session. All participants (100%) reported a decrease in pain to some degree between pre-session pain and during-session pain. The virtual reality experience was found here to provide a significant amount of pain relief. A head mounted display (HMD) was used with all subjects and no discomfort was experienced. Only one participant noted any side effects. VR seems to have promise as a non-opioid treatment for chronic pain and further investigation is warranted.

What:

VR is proven in a population of 30 subjects, to provide a 30% or more reduction in pain, tested with a paired t test with parameters $p < 0.001$ with three cases of 100% pain reduction.

How:

A quantitative scale of 0 to 10 for pain measurement was used before, during and after the 5 minute session in a population of 30 patients with chronic pain. The VR software is called cool! was used in the pain management therapy.

why:

VR is proven to be a pain management tool either as a substance substitute, thus simulating the efficacy of opioids and forming a possible non-opioid analgesic, as mindfulness based pain management or as a pain management mechanism by direct VR/AR, based two-world theories. VR may be more effective as it lacks withdrawal and addiction symptoms, making it a preferred treatment option, in cost effectiveness and ease of use.

Other Published Literature:

Based on a meta analysis of VR therapy for pain mitigation¹, the experimental parameters for the above study were based on this publication. While pain management, has been well studied in published literature, chronic pain mitigation needs further work,

A proof of concept study² in chronic lower back pain, using an integral approach at posture recovery, along with the management of mental wellness in patients, proving the efficacy of VR therapy in intervention, with several other non pharmaceutical approaches, including biofeedback and other therapies is described. The study involved 20 patients with VRRS based interventions for multimodal neuropsychological rehabilitation.

A review paper³ provides evidence of 18 publications on acute and chronic pain mitigation by multimodal therapies, with 12 proving a pain reduction mechanism in VR based intervention, five papers with inconclusive results and one result indicating worsening pain. The paper concludes with the need for further research in proving the adjunct use of VR therapy as a non-pharmacological therapy.

Impact: By google scholar, this paper has 98 citations.⁴

Potential Applications: Creating commercial VR products for pain management, both acute and chronic⁵.

Future Work: Given several commercial biomedical technologies and the use of VR and AR in home therapy, there is a vast market and a potential for the use of VR based technologies

in chronic pain management, the adjunct use with established therapies like acupuncture in pain management calls for the development of AR apps as CDSS systems for acupuncture home use. The ease of acupuncture training enables quick learning and self healing by patients. Several AR applications already exist such as Acuherb⁶.

References.

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6. AcuHerb System.

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